

Second Order Rotatable Designs of Second Type Using Pairwise Balanced Designs

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1 Introduction

Problems where several independent factors impact a dependent variable or response may be better understood with the use of response surface designs, a set of statistical and mathematical tools. Rotatable designs, first proposed by Box and Hunter [2], have a spherical variance function. The rotatable designs were created by Das and Narasimham [3] using BIBD, or balanced incomplete block designs. Second order rotatable designs (SORD) were built by Raghavarao [4] utilising incomplete block designs. An indicator of rotatability was proposed by Draper and Guttman [5]. For reaction surface designs, Khuri [6] established a rotatability measure. A new perspective on rotatability was created by Draper and Pukelshein [7]. The authors Park et al. [8] debuted novel measure of rotatability for second order response surface designs. Response surface designs that were changed were created by Das et al. [9]. Extended central composite designs (CCDs), first proposed by Kim [10], use two numerals to denote the axial points. Modified second-order response surface designs using BIBD were proposed by Victorbabu and Vasundharadevi [11]. Using two BIBD, Victorbabu [12] built a modified SORD. Research by Victorbabu et al. [13] examined pairwise balanced designs (PBD) as a means to modify second-order response surface designs. An examination of second-order rotatable designs was proposed by Victorbabu [14]. A second-order response surface design that makes use of CCD was proposed by Victorbabu et al. [14]. Using symmetrical uneven block arrangements (SUBA) with two

unequal block sizes, Victorbabu and Vasundharadevi [14] investigated second order response surface designs. Utilising a pair of SUBA with two uneven block sizes, Victorbabu [15] created modified SORD. For models of second-order response surfaces, Park & Park [16] proposed an expansion of CCD. In their work on incomplete block designs for second-order response surfaces, Victorbabu and Surekha [17] proposed a rotatability metric. In order to quantify the rotatability of second-order response surface designs, Victorbabu and Surekha [18] used BIBD. Two SUBAs with uneven block sizes and two BIBDs were used in the study of rotatability for second-order response surface designs by Victorbabu et al. [19,20]. According to Kim [21], extended CCD may be used to modify slope rotatability. Measures of modified rotatability for second-degree polynomials utilising BIBD, PBD, and SUBA with two unequal block sizes were investigated by Jyostna and Victorbabu [22,23,24]. As a metric for improved rotatability in second-order response surface designs using CCD, Jyostna et al. [25] proposed. The work of Kim [10] was expanded upon by Chiranjeevi et al. [26], who proposed second-type rotatable designs employing CCD for $9 \leq v \leq 17$ (where v is the number of components). Using SUBA with two uneven block sizes and BIBD, Chiranjeevi and Victorbabu [27,28] created SORD second type.

2 Conclusion

A second-type SORD that makes use of PBD is created in this work. We examined the variance and covariance of the calculated parameters and found that second-type SORDs utilising PBD are the most orthogonal for designs including second-order response surfaces; the publication also includes the findings of this evaluation.

Following an analysis of the relative efficiency of the two types of SORDs using PBD, we find that the second kind is more efficient, controlling for a variety of parameters. When compared to the first form of SORD employing PBD, this method is more efficient and easy to apply to real-world scenarios.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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